

COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE IN EMPOWERING RURAL MICRO, SMALL, AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (MSMEs): A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a strategic role in promoting economic growth and improving community welfare, particularly in rural areas. However, various challenges such as limited access to capital, low human resource capacity, restricted market access, and limited adoption of digital technology remain significant obstacles to MSME development. These conditions require the involvement of multiple stakeholders through a collaborative governance approach. This study aims to analyze the implementation of collaborative governance in rural MSME empowerment through a literature review. The study employs a literature review method by examining relevant scientific articles on collaborative governance and MSME empowerment. The analysis is based on the collaborative governance framework proposed by Ansell and Gash, which includes starting conditions, facilitative leadership, institutional design, and collaborative process. The findings indicate that the success of MSME empowerment is

influenced by synergy among government institutions, private sectors, academics, financial institutions, and communities. The government acts as a facilitator in coordinating stakeholders involved in empowerment programs. In addition, clear collaborative mechanisms and effective communication among stakeholders are important factors supporting program success. Therefore, collaborative governance can serve as an effective approach to improving the capacity, competitiveness, and sustainability of rural MSMEs.

Keywords: Collaborative Governance, MSME Empowerment, Rural MSMEs, Stakeholder Collaboration, Public Administration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are one of the sectors that have a significant contribution to the Indonesian economy. The role of MSMEs is not only seen from their ability to create jobs, but also in encouraging inclusive economic growth and equitable development. Various studies show that MSMEs are the backbone of the national economy with a large contribution to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and labor absorption in Indonesia (Faidati & Muthmainah, 2020; Amalia, 2025). The existence of MSMEs is also an important instrument in

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strengthening the economic resilience of the community, especially at the local and rural levels which still depend on economic activities based on micro and small enterprises.

Despite having a strategic role, MSMEs still face various problems that hinder business development. These various obstacles include limited access to capital, low human resource capacity, weak managerial skills, limited market access, and low utilization of digital technology in business activities (Faidati & Muthmainah, 2020; Amalia, 2025). In rural areas, these problems tend to be more complex because they are supported by limited infrastructure, uneven access to information, and a lack of partnership networks that can support sustainable business development.

The development of the strategic environment characterized by economic digitalization and increasing market competition requires MSMEs to be able to adapt to various changes. However, this adaptability cannot be fully imposed on MSME actors. The development of MSMEs requires support from various stakeholders who have different resources, authority, and capacities. Therefore, a sectoral development approach is considered no longer adequate to answer the complexity of the problems faced by MSMEs. A governance model is needed that is able to integrate various actors in one coordinated and sustainable cooperation mechanism (Kurniawan, Waspodo, & Putra, 2025).

In the context of public administration, the collaborative governance approach is one of the paradigms that is widely used to solve public problems involving many actors. Collaborative governance is a form of governance that involves the government, the private sector, the community, academics, and other stakeholders in the decision-making process and implementation of programs together to achieve agreed goals (Ansell & Gash, 2008). This approach places collaboration as the main instrument in building synergy, sharing resources, and creating more effective solutions to complex public problems.

The implementation of collaborative governance in empowering MSMEs has shown various positive results in a number of regions. Research by Faidati and Muthmainah (2020) shows that the development of MSMEs in the Special Region of Yogyakarta requires the involvement of the government, the private sector, and the community together in helping business actors adapt to changes in the business environment and technological developments. However, the study also found that the collaboration process has not run optimally because there is still overlap between the programs and target groups served.

Similar findings are also shown by the research of Rayhannisa and Pambudi (2024) regarding the SiBakul Jogja Program. The results of the study show that the success of MSME empowerment is determined by collaborative interaction involving local governments, the private sector, financial institutions, and business actors through training, capital, and product marketing support. However, the scope of the program is still limited and has not been able to reach all MSME actors evenly, so the effectiveness of collaboration still needs to be strengthened.

On the other hand, research by Kurniawan, Waspodo, and Putra (2025) emphasized that the success of economic empowerment programs through Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is greatly influenced by the ability of governments, companies, and communities to build participatory and sustainable collaborative governance. Collaboration that has not been integrated and weak coordination between actors have caused various empowerment programs to not be able to produce optimal impacts for the development of MSMEs.

These various studies show that collaborative governance has an important role in supporting the empowerment of MSMEs. However, most previous research still focused on case studies of specific regions, specific programs, and specific forms of collaboration. Studies that specifically identify the patterns, actors, mechanisms, and success factors of collaborative governance in empowering rural MSMEs comprehensively are still relatively limited. In fact, the

characteristics of rural areas have different challenges compared to urban areas, both in terms of institutions, resources, and the capacity of the actors involved.

Concept Based on these conditions, a study is needed that is able to synthesize various research findings on collaborative governance in rural MSME empowerment. This study is important to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the forms of effective collaboration, the actors that play a role, supporting and inhibiting factors, and their implications for the development of rural MSMEs. Thus, this study aims to analyze the development of collaborative governance studies in rural MSME empowerment through a literature study approach to produce a more systematic understanding of collaborative practices that can support the strengthening of the local economy in a sustainable manner.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Collaborative Governance

The concept of paradigm change in public administration has driven a shift from a hierarchical model of governance to more participatory and collaborative governance. The complexity of public problems involving many interests can no longer be solved by the government alone as a single actor. Therefore, the involvement of various stakeholders is needed in the process of formulating and implementing public policies.

One of the approaches that is developing in the study of public administration is *collaborative governance*. Ansell and Gash (2008) define *collaborative governance* as a governance arrangement that involves public institutions and non-government actors in the decision-making process in a collective, formal, consensus-oriented, and aimed at producing or implementing public policies. This approach emphasizes the importance of cooperation between stakeholders in solving complex public problems.

According to Ansell and Gash (2008), the success of *collaborative governance* is influenced by four main components, namely *starting conditions*, *facilitative leadership*, *institutional design*, and *collaborative process*. The four components are interrelated and determine the effectiveness of collaboration built between actors.

Table 1. Dimensions of Collaborative Governance According to Ansell and Gash (2008)

Dimensions	Description
Starting Conditions	The initial conditions that affect collaboration include resource distribution, trust level, and previous cooperation experience.
Facilitative Leadership	Leadership that functions to facilitate communication, mediate conflicts, and build mutual commitment.
Institutional Design	Rules, procedures, and mechanisms that govern relationships and interactions between actors in collaboration.

Collaborative Process	The interaction process includes dialogue, trust building, commitment, mutual understanding, and the achievement of common goals.
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[Sources: Ansell and Gash \(2008\); Rayhannisa and Pambudi \(2024\).](#)

In the context of regional development, *the collaborative governance* approach is relevant because it is able to integrate resources owned by the government, the private sector, academics, the community, and various other actors to achieve development goals more effectively and sustainably.

Empowerment of Rural MSMEs

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are economic sectors that have an important contribution to national and regional development. MSMEs play a role in creating jobs, increasing people's income, reducing poverty, and strengthening the local economic structure (Amalia, 2025). In addition, MSMEs have also proven to have relatively good survival skills in the face of various economic dynamics.

However, most MSMEs, especially those in rural areas, still face various obstacles in business development. Problems that are often found include limited access to capital, low quality of human resources, weak managerial capacity, limited market access, and low use of digital technology in business activities (Amalia, 2025). This condition causes the competitiveness of rural MSMEs to be relatively low compared to MSMEs that develop in urban areas.

MSME empowerment is basically a process of increasing the capacity of business actors to be able to develop their businesses independently and sustainably. Forms of empowerment can be carried out through training, mentoring, facilitation of access to financing, strengthening business institutions, developing marketing networks, and utilizing information technology (Rayhannisa & Pambudi, 2024). Therefore, the success of MSME empowerment is greatly influenced by the support of various parties involved in the business development process.

Collaborative Governance in MSME Empowerment

MSME empowerment is one of the fields of development that requires the involvement of various stakeholders. The complexity of the problems faced by business actors cannot be solved by the government independently, so synergy between the government, the private sector, academics, financial institutions, communities, and the community is needed.

Research by Faidati and Muthmainah (2020) shows that the success of MSME development is influenced by the ability of various actors to build collaboration to support business capacity building and digital transformation. However, the study also found obstacles in the form of coordination that was not optimal and the limited reach of the programs implemented.

Research by Rayhannisa and Pambudi (2024) regarding the SiBakul Jogja Program shows that collaborative interaction between stakeholders is able to support the empowerment of MSMEs through the provision of training, access to capital, and product marketing. The success of the program is supported by the involvement of local governments, the private sector, financial institutions, and business actors in the planning and implementation process of the program. Meanwhile, research by Kurniawan, Waspodo, and Putra (2025) shows that the implementation of *collaborative governance* in CSR-based economic empowerment programs is able to increase the effectiveness of program implementation through a clear division of roles and responsibilities

between actors. However, the challenge that is still found is that the coordination and sustainability of the collaboration that has been built has not been optimal.

The results of these studies show that *collaborative governance* has an important contribution in supporting the empowerment of MSMEs. Through effective collaboration, various resources owned by each actor can be integrated to increase business capacity, expand market access, strengthen capital, and encourage the digital transformation of MSMEs.

Table 2. Previous Research

Yes	Researcher	Research Focus	Key Findings
1.	Faidati & Muthmainah (2020)	Collaborative Governance in MSME Development	Collaboration supports the development of digital-based MSMEs but still faces coordination constraints.
2.	Pertiwi & Darumurti (2021)	A Free Trial Program	Collaboration between the government and the private sector expands MSME marketing access.
3.	Setyarini & Purnomo (2022)	SiBakul Jogja policy innovation	The digitalization of MSMEs requires strengthening data and coaching systems.
4.	Rayhannisa & Pambudi (2024)	Collaborative Governance in the SiBakul Jogja Program	The success of the program is determined by stakeholder synergy and facilitative leadership.
5.	Kurniawan, Waspodo, & Putra (2025)	CSR-based Collaborative Governance	Collaboration increases the effectiveness of community economic empowerment programs.

Source: Processed Author (2026).

Frame of Mind

This research departs from various problems faced by rural MSMEs, such as limited access to capital, low quality of human resources, limited market access, and low utilization of digital technology. These various problems require the involvement of many actors, so a *collaborative governance approach is needed*.

In this study, the analysis was carried out using *the collaborative governance* model developed by Ansell and Gash (2008), which consists of four main dimensions, namely *starting conditions, facilitative leadership, institutional design, and collaborative process*. The four dimensions are used to identify the forms of collaboration carried out in empowering rural MSMEs, the actors involved, supporting and inhibiting factors, and their impact on business development.

Figure 1. Research Thinking Framework

Source: Adapted from Ansell and Gash (2008) and developed by the author (2026).

This framework of thinking shows that collaborative governance is an important instrument in integrating various resources owned by stakeholders to support the empowerment of rural MSMEs in a sustainable manner.

3. METHODS

Types of Research

This study uses a *literature review* method to examine various research results related to *collaborative governance* in the empowerment of rural Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). The literature study was chosen because it allows researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of the concepts, collaboration patterns, and factors that affect the success of MSME empowerment based on previously published research.

Data Source

The data used in this study are secondary data derived from scientific journal articles, books, and supporting documents relevant to the research topic. Literature was obtained through various sources such as Google Scholar, Garuda, and national journals that discuss *collaborative governance* and MSME empowerment.

Data Collection Techniques

Data collection was carried out through tracing and reviewing various literature relevant to the research theme. The selected article is a publication that discusses the implementation of *collaborative governance* in MSME empowerment and was published in the range of 2020-2025.

Data Analysis Techniques

The data was analyzed using qualitative descriptive analysis techniques. The analysis was carried out by identifying, grouping, and comparing findings from various studies that had been selected. Furthermore, the results of the analysis were prepared based on the dimensions of *collaborative governance* according to Ansell and Gash (2008), namely *starting conditions*, *facilitative leadership*, *institutional design*, and *collaborative process*. The results of the analysis were used to explain the pattern of collaboration, the actors involved, as well as the supporting and inhibiting factors in empowering rural MSMEs.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Overview of Literature Reviewed

Based on the results of the literature search, a number of studies were found that discussed the application of *collaborative governance* in empowering MSMEs. These studies show that the success of MSME empowerment does not only depend on the role of the government, but also requires the involvement of the private sector, academics, financial institutions, and the community. Various forms of collaboration are carried out through training programs, business assistance, facilitation of access to capital, business digitalization, and marketing network development.

Table 3. Reviewed Articles

Yes	Author	Year	Study Focus	Key Findings
1	Faidati & Muthmainah	2020	Collaborative Governance MSMEs 4.0	Collaboration to support the development of digital-based MSMEs
2	Dharma & Darumurti	2021	Squirring is free of charge.	Government-private collaboration expands MSME marketing
3	Setyarini & Purnomo	2022	Innovative SiBakul Jogja	Digitalization of MSMEs requires continuous coaching
4	Rayhannisa & Pambudi	2024	Program SiBakul Jogja	Stakeholder synergy increases the effectiveness of MSME empowerment
5	Kurniawan, Waspodo, & Putra	2025	CSR-based Collaborative Governance	Collaboration to increase the effectiveness of economic empowerment programs

[Source: Processed Author \(2026\).](#)

The results of the study show that the *collaborative governance* approach has become one of the strategies that are widely used in empowering MSMEs because it is able to integrate the resources and capacities owned by various stakeholders.

Starting Conditions in Rural MSME Empowerment

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The starting *conditions* dimension explains the initial conditions behind the formation of collaboration. Based on various studies reviewed, rural MSMEs still face various fundamental problems such as limited business capital, low quality of human resources, limited market access, and low utilization of digital technology in business activities (Amalia, 2025). This condition causes most MSMEs to experience difficulties in increasing productivity and business competitiveness. In addition, the limited resources owned by the government are also an important reason for the need for the involvement of various actors in the MSME empowerment process. Thus, collaboration is a rational choice to overcome the various limitations faced by each party.

Research by Rayhannisa and Pambudi (2024) shows that the SiBakul Jogja Program was born as a response to various post-pandemic MSME problems, especially declining sales, marketing limitations, and low digital capabilities of business actors. The program then became a forum for collaboration between the government, the private sector, financial institutions, and MSME actors in supporting regional economic recovery.

Table 4. Early Conditions of Rural MSMEs Based on Literature

Problems	Impact
Capital limitations	Difficult to grow a business
Low HR	Low business productivity
Limited market access	Not optimal sales
Low digitalization	Difficult to compete in the modern market
Limitations of business networks	Difficult to expand partnerships

Source: Processed Author (2026).

The findings show that the initial conditions full of limitations are the main factor that encourages the formation of collaboration in empowering rural MSMEs.

Facilitative Leadership in Rural MSME Empowerment

The success of *collaborative governance* is greatly influenced by the existence of leadership that is able to facilitate inter-stakeholder interaction. In various studies reviewed, local governments play the role of the main actors who initiate, coordinate, and facilitate the collaborative process. The government not only acts as a regulator, but also as a facilitator who connects various parties to support the empowerment of MSMEs. In the SiBakul Jogja Program, the Yogyakarta Cooperatives and SMEs Office plays a role in integrating various stakeholders such as Grab, Gojek, Shopee, PT Pos Indonesia, Bank BPD DIY, and various other partners to support the marketing and development of MSME businesses.

Table 5. The Role of Stakeholders in MSME Empowerment

Stakeholder	Role
Government	Regulators and facilitators
Private	Technology and marketing support
Academics	Training and mentoring

Financial Institutions	Business financing
Society	Business participation and development

Source: Processed Author (2026).

The findings show that facilitative leadership has an important role in building communication, coordination, and commitment between actors involved in MSME empowerment.

Institutional Design in Rural MSME Empowerment

The institutional *design dimension* is related to the rules, mechanisms, and institutional structures that govern the collaboration process. The results of the study show that the success of collaboration is greatly influenced by the clarity of the division of roles, coordination mechanisms, and cooperation rules agreed upon by the parties.

The SiBakul Jogja program is an example of how a clear institutional design can support the implementation of collaboration effectively. The program provides a platform that connects the government, MSME actors, the private sector, and financial institutions in one integrated system. Through this system, various training, consulting, marketing, and financing programs can be implemented in a more structured manner (Rayhannisa & Pambudi, 2024). In addition, research by Kurniawan, Waspodo, and Putra (2025) shows that the existence of clear rules and cooperation mechanisms is able to increase the effectiveness of the implementation of CSR-based economic empowerment programs. A clear division of roles can also reduce the potential for conflict and overlapping authority between actors.

Thus, good institutional design is an important foundation in creating effective and sustainable collaboration.

Collaborative Process in Rural MSME Empowerment

The collaborative process is at the core of *collaborative governance*. This process is characterized by communication, dialogue, trust building, mutual commitment, and continuous cooperation between actors. The results of the study show that various successful MSME empowerment programs are generally supported by intensive interaction between the government, business actors, the private sector, and other stakeholders. Through a continuous communication process, the various needs of MSME actors can be identified and followed up through appropriate programs.

Figure 2. The Collaborative Governance Process in MSME Empowerment

Source: Adapted from Ansell and Gash (2008) and developed by the author (2026).

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Synthesis of Findings

Based on the results of the literature review, it was found that the implementation of *collaborative governance* in the empowerment of rural MSMEs is influenced by four main dimensions as stated by Ansell and Gash (2008).

Table 6. Synthesis of Research Findings

Dimensions	Key Findings
Starting Conditions	MSMEs face limited capital, human resources, market access, and digitalization
Facilitative Leadership	The government acts as a driver and facilitator of collaboration
Institutional Design	Clarity of rules and division of roles supports collaboration effectiveness
Collaborative Process	Communication, trust, and commitment increase program success

[Source: Processed Author \(2026\).](#)

Overall, the results of the study show that *collaborative governance* is a relevant approach in empowering rural MSMEs. The involvement of various stakeholders allows for resource integration, capacity building of business actors, expanding market access, and strengthening the competitiveness of MSMEs. However, the effectiveness of collaboration is still influenced by institutional capacity, the quality of inter-stakeholder coordination, and the sustainability of the commitment built in the collaboration process.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of a literature review on *collaborative governance* in empowering rural MSMEs, it can be concluded that a collaborative approach is one of the important strategies in overcoming various problems faced by MSMEs. Limited capital, low quality of human resources, limited market access, and low utilization of digital technology are the initial conditions that encourage the need for the involvement of various stakeholders in the MSME empowerment process.

The results of the study show that the success of the implementation of *collaborative governance* is influenced by four main dimensions stated by Ansell and Gash (2008), namely *starting conditions*, *facilitative leadership*, *institutional design*, and *collaborative process*. In the dimension of *starting conditions*, the various limitations that MSMEs have are the basis for the formation of inter-sector collaboration. In the *facilitative leadership* dimension, the government plays a role as a facilitator who connects various stakeholders in the MSME empowerment process. In the *institutional design dimension*, the existence of rules, cooperation mechanisms, and clear division of roles has been proven to support the effectiveness of collaboration. Meanwhile, in the dimension of *the collaborative process*, communication, trust, and commitment between actors are important factors in maintaining the sustainability of cooperation.

Various studies reviewed show that the involvement of the government, the private sector, academics, financial institutions, and the community is able to make a positive contribution to increasing the capacity of MSME actors through training, mentoring, access to capital, business digitalization, and expansion of marketing networks. Therefore, *collaborative governance* can be

seen as a relevant approach in supporting the empowerment of rural MSMEs in a sustainable manner.

Suggestions

Based on the results of the research, there are several suggestions that can be considered in an effort to increase the effectiveness of *collaborative governance* in empowering rural MSMEs.

1. The government needs to strengthen the coordination and facilitation function between stakeholders so that the MSME empowerment program can run in a more integrated and sustainable manner.
2. The involvement of the private sector, academia, and financial institutions needs to be continuously increased through more structured partnerships to support capacity building, access to capital, and digital transformation of MSMEs.
3. Strengthening collaborative institutions is needed through the preparation of clear cooperation mechanisms, proportional division of roles, and a continuous monitoring and evaluation system.
4. MSME empowerment programs need to be more directed towards improving digital capabilities, product innovation, and expanding market access so that rural MSMEs are able to increase competitiveness in the midst of the development of the digital economy.
5. The next research is suggested to conduct empirical studies in certain areas so that it can provide a more in-depth picture of the implementation of *collaborative governance* in the empowerment of rural MSMEs.

6. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Amalia. (2025). *Empowerment of MSMEs as a Strategy to Strengthen the Community Economy*. Journal of Administration and Public Policy.
- Ansell, C., & Gash, A. (2008). Collaborative governance in theory and practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), 543-571. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mum032>
- Bilqis, N., Alhadi, Z., & Putera, R. E. (2025). Collaborative governance in the implementation of smart cities as digital public service innovations in Indonesia. *Journal of Political and Social Sciences (JIPSK)*, 7(1), 1-15.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Emerson, K., Nabatchi, T., & Balogh, S. (2012). An integrative framework for collaborative governance. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 22(1), 1-29. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jopart/mur011>
- Faidati, N., & Muthmainah, M. (2020). *Collaborative Governance in the Development of MSMEs in the Era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0*. Journal of Public Administration.
- Feradiah, D., & Prianto, A. (2024). Strengthening the role of the government through collaborative governance in providing inclusive jobs in Pasuruan Regency. *Journal of Public*, 7(3), 1077-1093. <https://doi.org/10.35817/publicuho.v7i3.459>

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- Fitriyah, N. (2025). Agrarian conflict and land dispute resolution dynamics in Alastlogo Village, Pasuruan Regency. *Journal of Agrarian and Land*, 12(1), 45-58.
- Gash, C. A. (2008). Collaborative Governance in Theory and Practice. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory*, 18(4), 543-571.
- Kurniawan, A., Waspodo, T. S., & Putra, R. A. (2025). *Collaborative Governance in Community Economic Empowerment through Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) Programs*. Journal of State Administration.
- Pertiwi, D., & Darumurti, A. (2021). *Collaborative Governance in the Free Shipping SiBakul Program in Supporting MSMEs in the Special Region of Yogyakarta*. Journal of Public Policy and Management.
- Rayhannisa, N., & Pambudi, A. (2024). *Collaborative Governance in the SiBakul Jogja Program in MSME Empowerment*. Journal of State Administrative Sciences.
- Setyarini, D., & Purnomo, E. P. (2022). *SiBakul Jogja Policy Innovation in Digital-Based MSME Development*. Borneo Administrator Journal.